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54 **Method and device for measuring dielectrics in fluids**

57 The present invention relates to a method and device for measuring dielectrics in fluids, such as water, characterized by a first printed circuit board (PCB), a first conductor on the first side of said first PCB, a second conductor on the second side of said first PCB, a first polymer affinity layer and a second polymer affinity layer on top of the first and second sides of the first PCB respectively, a second PCB equipped with holes and a first conductor plate placed on top of the first affinity layer and a third PCB equipped with holes and a second conductor plate placed on top of the second affinity layer. The result is a sensor consisting of a first PCB sandwiched between the first and second polymer affinity layers and between the second and third PCBs. The sensor is placed in the fluid under investigation and the polymer affinity layers in the sensor absorb chemical compounds and / or ions present in the fluid. At lower frequencies the sensor acts as a capacitive sensor, where absorbed compounds can be characterized by changes in the capacitor value and in the losses. At higher frequencies, the sensor behaves electrically as a stub resonator, the absorbed compounds and / or ions can be characterized or identified through impedance spectroscopy.

Method and device for measuring dielectrics in fluids

The present invention relates to a method and device for measuring dielectrics in fluids, such as water, characterized by a first printed circuit board (PCB), a first conductor on the first side of said first PCB, a second conductor on the second side of said first PCB, a first
5 polymer affinity layer and a second polymer affinity layer on top of the first and second sides of the first PCB respectively, a first conductor plate with holes, on top of the first affinity layer that is supported by a second PCB and a second conductor plate with holes, placed on top of the second affinity layer that is supported by a third PCB. The result is a sensor consisting of a first PCB sandwiched between the first and second polymer affinity
10 layers and between the second and third PCBs. The sensor is placed in the fluid under investigation and the polymer affinity layers in the sensor absorb chemical compounds and / or ions present in the fluid. Since the sensor behaves electrically as a stub resonator, the absorbed compounds and / or ions can be characterized or identified through impedance spectroscopy.

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Introduction

Nowadays, the main way of measuring contaminants in water is grab-sampling, i.e. sending the samples to a lab and waiting for the results. This invention relates to a sensor that can be placed in-line and read-out remotely, giving the analysis results real-time. Other (similar)
20 devices are limited because of parasitic effects, have a limited range (frequency and concentration) and / or are sensitive to defects. A key aspect of the present invention concerns the geometry of the device. The proposed geometry ensures that essentially all electric field lines run through the affinity layer. Prevention of stray field lines (i.e. lines reaching out of the affinity layer) to surrounding dielectric and conductive material makes
25 the sensor insensitive to changing dielectric conditions outside the affinity layer. By implication, the sensitivity of the sensor solely depends on the change of the dielectric properties accomplished by the targeted analyte that has been absorbed by the affinity layer. Fine tuning the chemistry of the affinity layer allows the design of sensors with different affinities for different analytes. This opens possibilities for designing a product
30 range of sensors with selectivity for different analytes.

Technical description of the present invention

The different aspects of the technology according to the present invention are now described. In order to explain the invention, figures 1 to 3 will be used.
35 According to a first aspect, the present invention relates to a first, preferably rectangular PCB, indicated in the cross section perpendicular to the length axis of the sensor in figure 1 with numbers 4, 5 and 6. The first PCB is equipped with two, preferably identical,

conductors 4 and 6 that are present on each side of said first PCB. The geometry of conductors 4 and 6 is preferably identical and their position on the first PCB is preferably such that both conductors are exactly on top of each other with the first PCB substrate in between. Preferably, both conductors 4 and 6 on each side of the first PCB are galvanically
5 connected, either through one connection point or more preferably through a series of vias along the length coordinate of the first PCB. In this patent application, a via is defined as a metal-plated hole in a PCB, galvanically connecting a conductor on one side of the PCB to a conductor on the other side of the PCB. This design of the first PCB results in one electrode that can be applied in a design of two parallel capacitors, behaving like a stub
10 resonator at high frequencies, without the substrate dielectric 5 of the first PCB influencing the dielectric properties of said two parallel capacitors. This will be further explained later in the text of this patent application. In figure 2, the PCB design indicated with number 12 shows a preferred embodiment of a first PCB. At the left side of PCB number 12, the connection points of an SMA connector can be seen. It is noted that, obviously, these
15 contacts can also be used for making wire connections and also that other kinds of electrical connections can be made. The straight line at the center of the PCB with number 12 (figure 2) shows conductor 4 in figure 1 located on the top side of the first PCB. There is also a conductor 6 at the bottom side of the first PCB. Both conductors 4 and 6 are positioned at the center of the first PCB, exactly above each other with the substrate 5 of
20 the first PCB in between. Both conductors 4 and 6 are galvanically connected at the SMA connection point at the left side of PCB number 12 in figure 2. It is noted that, more preferably, both conductors 4 and 6 on each side of the first PCB are interconnected through vias along the length coordinate of the first PCB. These vias are not depicted in figure 2.

25 According to a third aspect, the present invention relates to a second PCB, equipped with holes and a first conductor plate 2, placed on top of the first affinity layer 3 and a third PCB, equipped with holes and a second conductor plate 8, placed below the second affinity layer 7. In figure 1, the numbers 1, 9 and 2, 8 indicate the substrates (numbers 1 and 9) and the conductor plates (numbers 2 and 8) of both preferably identical second and third PCBs
30 respectively. In figure 2, the rectangular PCBs, indicated with numbers 10 and number 13, show practical examples of second and third PCBs. It is noted that the conductor plates of the second and third PCBs are not shown on the perforated PCBs with number 10 and 13 in figure 2. Further, it is noted that the conductor plates 2 and 8 of the second and third PCBs have holes at exactly the same spot as the holes in the substrate of the second and
35 third PCBs. Finally, it is noted that the conductor plates 2 and 8 of the second and third PCB are galvanically connected through connectors and / or wires and / or any other conductor. The result is that the first PCB and the second PCB form a first capacitor and

that the first PCB and the third PCB form a second capacitor. It is noted that, from an electrical point of view, the first and second capacitors are positioned in parallel.

After describing the different aspects of the present invention, the technology according to the present invention will now be further explained. It is noted that, in this patent

5 application, the term PCB stands for a printed circuit board comprising both a support layer (preferably FR4 material) and any conductors on this support layer.

In a nutshell, the sensor in figure 1 comprises the electrical equivalent of two capacitors in parallel: A first capacitor formed by the first PCB and the second PCB with the polymer affinity layer 3 as dielectric in between and a second capacitor formed by the first PCB and
10 the third PCB with the polymer affinity layer 7 as dielectric in between. Let us now assume that a sensor according to figure 1 is placed in water containing impurities that are selectively absorbed by polymer affinity layers 3 and 7. Placing the sensor in figure 1 in water will result in contact between the water and the polymer affinity layers 3 and 7, mainly through the holes in the second and third PCBs. As a result, the polymer affinity layer will
15 selectively absorb the impurities in the water. As a result of diffusion, the impurities will be distributed over the polymer affinity layers 3 and 7 thereby changing the dielectric properties of these layers. Because of the very specific design of the sensor in figure 1, the capacitance of the sensor will only change because of changing dielectric properties of polymer affinity layer 3 and not directly because of a change in the dielectric properties of
20 the water in which the sensor is placed. Additionally, the dielectric properties of the substrate of the first, second and third PCBs do not significantly influence the capacitance of the sensor, thereby making it more sensitive as compared to designs where the sensor capacitance is also a function of the dielectric properties of the PCB substrate. This property of the sensor is caused by its geometry which is such that all the electrical field
25 lines go through polymer affinity layer 3. As a result, the sensor according to the present invention is very feasible as inline sensor i.e., it can be placed in the fluid to be investigated. In a preferred embodiment, the sensor according to figure 1 is placed in a first housing e.g., a cylinder or another water container with a fluid inlet and a fluid outlet. The fluid under investigation is pumped through the first housing such that it flows along the
30 holes in the second and third PCBs. As a result, there is fast mass transfer of impurities in the fluid to the polymer affinity layers 3 and 7, thereby reducing the response time of the sensor.

As explained above, the sensor can be applied as an inline capacitance sensor to detect changes in water quality and the chemical composition of aqueous solutions. This
35 application makes expressly part of the technology of the present invention.

In the following, it will be explained that the technology of the present invention is very feasible for impedance spectroscopy. The geometry of the sensor in figure 1 is such that

this sensor is an electrical equivalent of a piece of coaxial transmission line. Figure 3 gives a schematic overview of a coaxial transmission line. In figure 3, the number 14 indicates the inner conductor of the coaxial transmission line, the number 15 indicates the outer conductor of the coaxial transmission line and the number 16 indicates the dielectric of the coaxial transmission line, usually a polymer. All field lines between the inner conductor 14 and the outer conductor 15 go through dielectric 16. A piece of transmission line is known to have a capacitance, an inductance and to behave like a stub resonator. This property makes transmission line based sensors very feasible for impedance spectroscopy i.e., for studying the properties of a dielectric 2 as a function of frequency. As a result, not only the static capacitance of the dielectric, but also its dielectric losses as a function of frequency can be studied. Analogous to figure 3, the sensor design in figure 1, consisting of PCBs with numbers 10, 12 and 13 in figure 2, behaves like a stub resonator. Hence, it is possible to measure real time and inline the change of dielectric properties of the polymer affinity layers 3 and 7 in figure 1 as a function of frequency without disturbance of the (changing) dielectric properties of surrounding water that are not directly related to the analyte of interest. This property makes the technology of the present invention unique as compared to prior art.

Preferably, the sensor is connected to an input/output (laboratory) device (spectrum analyzer or a simple computer system like e.g., the raspberry-pi), which can generate an excitation signal with a frequency in the range of 100 kHz to 3 GHz, and can be connected to a small computer platform for remotely reading-out the sensor device. Alternatively, a frequency generator or function generator and a rectifier for measuring the amplitude of the signal can be applied. The spectrum analyzer, frequency or function generator and rectifier are operatively connected to the sensor through transmission lines. It is noted that operating frequencies of the sensor system outside the frequency range from 100 kHz to 3 GHz are not excluded and expressly make part of the technology of the present invention. The sensor according to the present invention is also unique because it is easy to manufacture: The first, second and third PCBs can be produced using standard PCB manufacturing techniques. The PCBs can be immobilized and connected easily through connectors such as plastic screws. Alternatively or additionally, spacers, such as plastic beads or glass beads, can be put between the PCBs so that there is a uniform distance between them. Subsequently, the PCBs can be placed in a mould and the polymer affinity layer can be poured into the mould. After cross linking and electrically connecting the sensor, it is ready for use. This method of production makes expressly part of the technology according to the present invention.

From a practical point of view, it may be desirable to produce a sensor with a relatively low

resonant frequency. Since the resonant frequency decreases with increasing length of the conductors on the first PCB in figure 1, a low resonant frequency of the sensor may require unacceptably long PCBs. It is noted that this problem can be overcome by application of meander conductors on both sides of the first PCB. An example of meander conductors on a PCB is shown in figure 2, PCB number 11. In order to ensure that all field lines go through the polymer affinity layer, the width of the meander should be limited. The width of the meander shown on PCB number 11 in figure 2 is most probably unacceptably high, resulting in field lines leaving the sensor and going through the water in which the sensor is submerged. A first PCB with meandering conductors as depicted in figure 2, PCB number 11 expressly makes part of the present invention. As will be explained later in this patent application, additional guard electrodes can be applied to ensure that all field lines go through the polymer affinity layer. The combination of a first PCB with meandering conductors as depicted in figure 2, PCB number 11 with guard electrodes, expressly makes part of the present invention.

It is noted that the straight line at the center of the PCB with number 12 (figure 2) suggests that the width of conductors 4 and 6 in figure 1 must be very small. In fact, this is not the case. In a first preferred embodiment of the present invention, the surface of the PCB in the center i.e., PCB 5 in figure 1, is completely covered with conductive material, because this will decrease the sensitivity for surface effects. Increasing the width of conductors 4 and 6 will result in a capacitance increase of the sensor and in a change of the resonant frequencies of the sensor when it is operated at high frequencies i.e., as a stub resonator. In a second preferred embodiment of the present invention, the width of conductors 4 and 6 is used as a design parameter to achieve the desired sensor properties in terms of resonant frequencies and characteristic impedance in case it is operated as a stub resonator at high frequencies.

Figure 4 shows a cross section of a sensor similar to the sensor described in figure 1. The width of the conductors 22 and 28 on the PCB in the center (PCB 25) is increased as compared to the previously explained situation shown in figure 2, PCB number 12. An undesired effect of the increased width of conductors 22 and 28 is the increased number of electrical field lines leaving the "sandwich geometry" of the sensor and traveling through the dielectric (such as water) in which the sensor is placed i.e., from conductor 28 through the dielectric (such as water) to conductor 31 and from conductor 22 through the dielectric (such as water) to conductor 20 respectively. This will only happen when the distance between the edge of the conductors 22 and 28 and the edge of the affinity layers 21 and 29 is less than about 3 times the thickness of the affinity layers 21 and 29. In case this undesired effect occurs, the sensor will become more sensitive to changes in properties of

the dielectric surrounding the sensor that are not directly related to the analyte to be detected. In order to prevent this undesired effect of increasing the width of conductors 22 and 28, the sensor can be equipped with guard electrodes 23, 24, 26, 27. The width of the guard electrodes 22 and 28 shown in figure 4 is too small for most applications. This width should be at least 3 times that of the thickness of the affinity layers 21 and 29. In figure 4, conductors 23 and 24 are galvanically separated from conductor 22 and conductors 26 and 27 are galvanically separated from conductor 28. The guard electrodes 23, 24, 26 and 27 are preferably galvanically connected forming one guard electrode. Analogous to figure 1, the conductors 22 and 28 on PCB 25 in figure 4 (the center of the sandwich) are galvanically connected and form the first sensing electrode. Hence, we have a first sensing electrode, consisting of galvanically connected conductors 22 and 28, that is guarded with a guard electrode consisting of galvanically connected conductors 23, 24, 26, 27. Similarly, galvanically connected conductors 20 and 30 are galvanically connected and form the second sensing electrode that is optionally guarded by guard electrodes 18, 19, 31 and 32. Hence we have a second sensing electrode, consisting of galvanically connected conductors 20 and 30, that is guarded with a guard electrode consisting of galvanically connected conductors 18, 19, 31, 32. In a third preferred embodiment of the present invention, guard electrodes 18, 19, 23, 24, 26, 27, 31, 32 are all galvanically connected and grounded or held at a fixed potential and neither galvanically connected to the first sensing electrode nor to the second sensing electrode. A non limiting example of connecting the guard electrodes is to apply active guarding. With active guarding the guard electrodes 23, 24, 26 and 27 are connected with the voltage source, where the voltage is equal to that of the voltage of electrodes 22 and 28. This can be realized for instance with a unity-gain amplifier while applying negative feedback. Instead of negative feedback, active guarding can also be realized with feedforward principles, which will reduce the risk of occurrence of undesired oscillations. In a fourth preferred embodiment of the present invention, guard electrodes 18, 19, 23, 24, 26, 27, 31, 32 are all galvanically connected to the second sensing electrode, which is grounded or held at a fixed potential. It is noted that, in this fourth embodiment, guard electrodes 18, 19, 31, 32 can be omitted and that, instead, the width of conductors 20 and 30 can be increased. An important design parameter for the sensor according to the present invention is the distance between the guard electrodes 18, 19, 23, 24, 26, 27, 31, 32 and the first and second electrodes respectively. For example, a very small distance between guard electrodes 23, 24 on one hand and conductor 22 on the other hand, will keep field lines inside the sensor but will also result in a large parasitic capacitance, decreasing the

sensitivity of the sensor.

According to a second aspect, the present invention relates to a first polymer affinity layer 3 that is placed on top of the first PCB and second polymer affinity layer 7 that is placed below the first PCB, see also figure 1. Polymer affinity layers 3 and 7 may consist of a
5 functionalized polymer, such as PDMS or chemically modified PDMS, designed to specifically absorb a targeted analyte.

It is noted that, although the sensor according to the present invention is very feasible to be operated as a stub resonator at high frequencies, it can also be applied for capacitance measurements at low frequencies i.e., at frequencies (far) below the lowest stub resonator
10 resonant frequency of the sensor or, in other words, far below the base resonant frequency of the sensor in case it is applied as a quarter wave length open ended stub resonator. A typical frequency range for operating the sensor for capacitance measurements is 0 Hz (DC) to 100 kHz. Application of the sensor according to the present invention at frequencies below the lowest stub resonator resonant frequency of the sensor, expressly makes part of
15 the present invention.

Regarding the construction materials indicated with numbers 1, 5 and 7 in figure 1, until now assumed to be printed circuit board construction material e.g., glass reinforced epoxy laminate sheets, FR4 material, it is noted that also glass, ceramics and any other (water) resistant materials are very feasible support materials for the conductors in figure 1.
20 Regarding the affinity layers 3 and 7 in figure 1, it is noted that besides PDMS or chemically modified PDMS, also other polymers e.g., polyethylene-co-vinylacetate are very feasible. The polymer polyethylene-co-vinylacetate is especially feasible for detection of VOCs (volatile organic compounds). Dodecyl acrylates are very feasible for the production of affinity layers selective for lead ions. For the detection of polar VOCs, polysiloxanes
25 modified with polar units like SFXA are very feasible. The abbreviation FPOL stands for molecular structures like structure 34 in figure 5. The abbreviation SFXA stands for molecular structures like structure 35, 36 and 37 in figure 5. Sensors with an affinity layer containing at least 1 ppm of beforementioned molecules expressly makes part of the present invention.

30 In the following a number of non-limiting application examples of the sensor are mentioned. In a first application the sensor is applied to detect traces of hydrophobic compounds (or metabolites thereof) like oil traces and polychlorinated biphenyls in water.

In a second application the sensor is applied to detect traces of metal ions or heavy metal ions like lead ions in water.

35 In a third application, the sensor is applied to detect nutrients in water such as phosphates, nitrates and sulfates.

In a fourth application, the sensor is applied to detect detergents in water including non-

ionic detergents e.g., pentaerythryl palmitate and ionic detergents e.g., sodium dodecyl sulfate.

In a fifth application the sensor is applied to detect medicine (or metabolites thereof) traces in water.

- 5 In a sixth application the sensor is applied to detect pesticides, (or metabolites thereof) in water.

In a seventh application, the sensor is applied to detect traces of drugs in water e.g., narcotics, XTC and cocaine.

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Clauses

1. Sensor for measuring the dielectric properties of chemical compounds and / or ions in water characterized by
 - 5 • characterized by a first printed circuit board (PCB),
 - a first conductor on the first side of said first PCB,
 - a second conductor on the second side of said first PCB,
 - at least one galvanic connection between the first conductor and the second conductor
 - a first polymer affinity layer on top of the first side of the first PCB
 - 10 • a second polymer affinity layer on top of the second side of the first PCB
 - a second PCB equipped with holes and a first conductor plate placed on top of the first polymer affinity layer
 - a third PCB equipped with holes and a second conductor plate placed on top of the second polymer affinity layer
 - 15 • at least one galvanic connection between the first conductor plate and the second conductor plate
 - at least a first function generator, operatively to the first and second conductors as well as to the first and second conductor plates
 - at least a first spectrum analyzer or rectifier, operatively connected to the first and second conductors as well as to the first and second conductor plate for measuring the amplitude of the electrical signal transmitted from the function generator through the measuring system
 - 20
2. Sensor according to clause 1, where the first and second conductors are galvanically interconnected through at least 2 vias on the PCB.
- 25 3. Sensor according to one of the previous clauses 1 and 2, a housing with a fluid inlet and a fluid outlet in which the sensor is placed and submerged in the water under investigation.
4. Sensor according to one of the previous clauses 1 to 3 where the first and second conductors of the first PCB meander over the PCB surface thereby increasing the effective length of said conductors.
- 30 5. Sensor according to one of the previous clauses 1 to 4 for the detection of oil traces in water.
6. Sensor according to one of the previous clauses 1 to 4 for the detection of metal ions in water.
- 35 7. Sensor according to one of the previous clauses 1 to 4 for the detection of medicine traces in water.
8. Sensor according to one of the previous clauses 1 to 4 for the detection of

pesticides in water.

9. Sensor according to one of the previous clauses 1 to 4 for the detection of traces of drugs in water e.g., narcotics, XTC and cocaine.
- 5 10. Sensor according to one of the previous clauses 1 to 4 to detect detergents in water including non-ionic detergents e.g., pentaerythrityl palmitate and ionic detergents e.g., sodium dodecyl sulfate.
11. Sensor according to one of the previous clauses 1 to 4 to detect nutrients in water such as phosphates, nitrates and sulfates.
- 10 12. Sensor according to one of the previous clauses 1 to 11 operated at a frequency of the first function generator below its quarter wave length open ended stub resonator resonant frequency.
13. Sensor according to clause 12 operated at a frequency of the first function generator below 100 kHz.
- 15 14. Sensor according to clause 13 for measuring the dielectric losses in the first and second polymer affinity layers.
15. Method for a sensor to measure the dielectric properties of chemical compounds and / or ions in water characterized by a device according to clauses 1-14.

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Conclusies

1. Sensor voor het meten van de dielectrische eigenschappen van chemische verbindingen en / of ionen in water gekenmerkt door
 - een eerste printplaat (PCB),
 - 5 • een eerste geleider op de eerste zijde van de eerste PCB,
 - een tweede geleider geleider op de tweede zijde van de eerste PCB,
 - tenminste een galvanische verbinding tussen de eerste geleider en de tweede geleider,
 - een eerste polymere affiniteitslaag op de eerste zijde van de eerste PCB,
 - 10 • een tweede polymere affiniteitslaag op de tweede zijde van de eerste PCB,
 - een tweede PCB, voorzien van gaten en een eerste geleiderplaat, die bovenop de eerste polymere affiniteitslaag is geplaatst,
 - een derde PCB, voorzien van gaten en een tweede geleiderplaat, die bovenop de tweede polymere affiniteitslaag is geplaatst,
 - 15 • tenminste een galvanische verbinding tussen de eerste geleiderplaat en de tweede geleiderplaat,
 - tenminste een eerste functiegenerator die werkzaam is verbonden met de eerste en tweede geleiders en met de eerste en tweede geleiderplaten,
 - tenminste een spectrum analyzer of gelijkrichter die werkzaam is verbonden met
 - 20 de eerste en tweede geleiders en met de eerste en tweede geleiderplaten voor het meten van de amplitude van het elektrische signaal dat door de functiegenerator in het meetsysteem wordt gebracht.
2. Sensor volgens conclusie 1 met het kenmerk dat de eerste geleider en de tweede geleider op de eerste PCB door middel van tenminste 2 via's met elkaar verbonden
- 25 zijn.
3. Sensor volgens een van de voorgaande conclusies 1 en 2 vermeerderd met een behuizing waarin de sensor is geplaatst, die is voorzien van een vloeistofinlaat en een vloeistofuitlaat, waarbij de sensor in de behuizing tenminste deels is ondergedompeld in het water waarmee de behuizing wordt doorstroomd.
- 30 4. Sensor volgens een van de voorgaande conclusies 1 t/m 3 waarbij de eerste geleider en de tweede geleider van de eerste PCB over het oppervlak van de eerste PCB meanderen zodat de effectieve lengte van de geleiders groter is dan de lengte van de eerste PCB.
5. Sensor volgens een van de voorgaande conclusies 1 t/m 4 voor de detectie van
- 35 sporen olie in water.
6. Sensor volgens een van de voorgaande conclusies 1 t/m 4 voor de detectie van metaalionen in water.

7. Sensor volgens een van de voorgaande conclusies 1 t/m 4 voor de detectie van medicijnresten in water.
8. Sensor volgens een van de voorgaande conclusies 1 t/m 4 voor de detectie van pesticiden in water.
- 5 9. Sensor volgens een van de voorgaande conclusies 1 t/m 4 voor de detectie van opiaten of XTC of cocaine.
10. Sensor volgens een van de voorgaande conclusies 1 t/m 4 voor de detectie van detergents in water.
11. Sensor volgens een van de voorgaande conclusies 1 t/m 4 voor de detectie van fosfaten, nitraten, sulfaten in water.
- 10 12. Sensor volgens een van de voorgaande conclusies 1 t/m 11 bedreven bij een frequentie van de eerste functiegenerator die lager is dan de grondfrequentie van de kwart golflengte open ended stub resonator uitvoeringsvorm van de sensor.
13. Sensor volgens een van de voorgaande conclusies 1 t/m 12 waarbij de eerste
15 functiegenerator wordt bedreven op tenminste een frequentie beneden 100 kHz.
14. Sensor volgens een van de voorgaande conclusies 1 t/m 13 voor het meten van dielectrische verliezen in de eerste en tweede polymere affiniteitslaag.
15. Werkwijze voor een inrichting om de dielektrische eigenschappen van chemische
20 verbindingen en / of ionen in water te meten gekenmerkt door een sensor volgens een van de voorgaande conclusies 1 t/m 14.

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Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Abstract

The present invention relates to a method and device for measuring dielectrics in fluids, such as water, characterized by a first printed circuit board (PCB), a first conductor on the first side of said first PCB, a second conductor on the second side of said first PCB, a first
5 polymer affinity layer and a second polymer affinity layer on top of the first and second sides of the first PCB respectively, a second PCB equipped with holes and a first conductor plate placed on top of the first affinity layer and a third PCB equipped with holes and a second conductor plate placed on top of the second affinity layer. The result is a sensor consisting of a first PCB sandwiched between the first and second polymer affinity layers
10 and between the second and third PCBs. The sensor is placed in the fluid under investigation and the polymer affinity layers in the sensor absorb chemical compounds and / or ions present in the fluid. At lower frequencies the sensor acts as a capacitive sensor, where absorbed compounds can be characterized by changes in the capacitor value and in the losses. At higher frequencies, the sensor behaves electrically as a stub
15 resonator, the absorbed compounds and / or ions can be characterized or identified through impedance spectroscopy.

ONDERZOEKSRAPPORT

BETREFFENDE HET RESULTAAT VAN HET ONDERZOEK NAAR DE STAND VAN DE TECHNIEK

RELEVANTE LITERATUUR

Categorie	Literatuur met, voor zover nodig, aanduiding van tekstgedeelten of figuren.	Van belang voor conclusie(s) nr.	Classificatie (IPC)
A	NL 1 040 124 C (SMART FREQUENCIES B V) 25 september 2014 (2014-09-25) * bladzijde 3, regel 14 - bladzijde 4, regel 27; figuren *	1-15	INV. G01N27/02 G01N22/00
A	HOOG N A ET AL: "Stub resonators for online monitoring early stages of corrosion", SENSORS AND ACTUATORS B: CHEMICAL: INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL DEVOTED TO RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL TRANSDUCERS, ELSEVIER BV, NL, deel 202, 16 juni 2014 (2014-06-16), bladzijden 1117-1136, XP029009248, ISSN: 0925-4005, DOI: 10.1016/J.SNB.2014.06.026 * bladzijde 1118, rechter kolom, alinea 2 - bladzijde 1121, alinea 1; figuren *	1-15	
A	KHALIFEH R ET AL: "Development of a radio frequency resonator for monitoring water diffusion in organic coatings", SENSORS AND ACTUATORS A: PHYSICAL, ELSEVIER BV, NL, deel 247, 20 mei 2016 (2016-05-20), bladzijden 30-36, XP029713734, ISSN: 0924-4247, DOI: 10.1016/J.SNA.2016.05.024 * bladzijde 31, linker kolom, alinea 2 - rechter kolom, alinea 1; figuur 3 *	1-15	Onderzochte gebieden van de techniek G01N

Indien gewijzigde conclusies zijn ingediend, heeft dit rapport betrekking op de conclusies ingediend op:

Plaats van onderzoek:

's-Gravenhage

Datum waarop het onderzoek werd
voltooid:

7 september 2017

Bevoegd ambtenaar:

Savage, John

CATEGORIE VAN DE VERMELDE LITERATUUR

- X: de conclusie wordt als niet nieuw of niet inventief beschouwd ten opzichte van deze literatuur
- Y: de conclusie wordt als niet inventief beschouwd ten opzichte van de combinatie van deze literatuur met andere geciteerde literatuur van dezelfde categorie, waarbij de combinatie voor de vakman voor de hand liggend wordt geacht
- A: niet tot de categorie X of Y behorende literatuur die de stand van de techniek beschrijft
- O: niet-schriftelijke stand van de techniek
- P: tussen de voorzugsdatum en de indieningsdatum gepubliceerde literatuur

- T: na de indieningsdatum of de voorzugsdatum gepubliceerde literatuur die niet bezwaard is voor de octrooiaanvraag, maar wordt vermeld ter verheldering van de theorie of het principe dat ten grondslag ligt aan de uitvinding
- E: eerdere octrooi(aanvraag), gepubliceerd op of na de indieningsdatum, waarin dezelfde uitvinding wordt beschreven
- D: in de octrooiaanvraag vermeld
- L: om andere redenen vermelde literatuur
- S: lid van dezelfde octrooifamilie of overeenkomstige octrooipublicatie

**AANHANGSEL BEHORENDE BIJ HET RAPPORT BETREFFENDE
HET ONDERZOEK NAAR DE STAND VAN DE TECHNIEK,
UITGEVOERD IN DE OCTROOIAANVRAGE NR.**

NO 139831
NL 1042400

Het aanhangsel bevat een opgave van elders gepubliceerde octrooiaanvragen of octrooien (zogenaamde leden van dezelfde octroofamilie), die overeenkomen met octrooischriften genoemd in het rapport.

De opgave is samengesteld aan de hand van gegevens uit het computerbestand van het Europees Octrooibureau per
De juistheid en volledigheid van deze opgave wordt noch door het Europees Octrooibureau, noch door het Bureau voor de Industriële eigendom gegarandeerd; de gegevens worden verstrekt voor informatiedoeleinden.

07-09-2017

In het rapport genoemd octrooigeschrift	Datum van publicatie	Overeenkomend(e) geschrift(en)	Datum van publicatie
NL 1040124	C	25-09-2014	GEEN

SCHRIFTELIJKE OPINIE

DOSSIER NUMMER NO139831	INDIENINGSDATUM 24.05.2017	VOORRANGSDATUM	AANVRAAGNUMMER NL1042400
CLASSIFICATIE INV. G01N27.02 G01N22.00			
AANVRAGER Stichting Wetsus, European Centre of Excellence for Sustainable Water Technology			

Deze schriftelijke opinie bevat een toelichting op de volgende onderdelen:

- Onderdeel I Basis van de schriftelijke opinie
- Onderdeel II Voorrang
- Onderdeel III Vaststelling nieuwheid, inventiviteit en industriële toepasbaarheid niet mogelijk
- Onderdeel IV De aanvraag heeft betrekking op meer dan één uitvinding
- Onderdeel V Gemotiveerde verklaring ten aanzien van nieuwheid, inventiviteit en industriële toepasbaarheid
- Onderdeel VI Andere geciteerde documenten
- Onderdeel VII Overige gebreken
- Onderdeel VIII Overige opmerkingen

DE BEVOEGDE AMBTENAAR Savage, John

SCHRIFTELIJKE OPINIE

Aanvraag nr.:

NL1042400

Onderdeel I Basis van de Schriftelijke Opinie

1. Deze schriftelijke opinie is opgesteld op basis van de meest recente conclusies ingediend voor aanvang van het onderzoek.
2. Met betrekking tot **nucleotide en/of aminozuur sequenties** die genoemd worden in de aanvraag en relevant zijn voor de uitvinding zoals beschreven in de conclusies, is dit onderzoek gedaan op basis van:
 - a. type materiaal:
 - sequentie opsomming
 - tabel met betrekking tot de sequentie lijst
 - b. vorm van het materiaal:
 - op papier
 - in elektronische vorm
 - c. moment van indiening/aanlevering:
 - opgenomen in de aanvraag zoals ingediend
 - samen met de aanvraag elektronisch ingediend
 - later aangeleverd voor het onderzoek
3. In geval er meer dan één versie of kopie van een sequentie opsomming of tabel met betrekking op een sequentie is ingediend of aangeleverd, zijn de benodigde verklaringen ingediend dat de informatie in de latere of additionele kopieën identiek is aan de aanvraag zoals ingediend of niet meer informatie bevatten dan de aanvraag zoals oorspronkelijk werd ingediend.
4. Overige opmerkingen:

SCHRIFTELIJKE OPINIE

Aanvraag nr.:
NL1042400

Onderdeel V Gemotiveerde verklaring ten aanzien van nieuwheid, inventiviteit en industriële toepasbaarheid

1. Verklaring

Nieuwheid	Ja: Conclusies 1-15 Nee: Conclusies
Inventiviteit	Ja: Conclusies 1-15 Nee: Conclusies
Industriële toepasbaarheid	Ja: Conclusies 1-15 Nee: Conclusies

2. Citaties en toelichting:

Zie aparte bladzijde

Onderdeel VIII Overige opmerkingen

De volgende opmerkingen met betrekking tot de duidelijkheid van de conclusies, beschrijving, en figuren, of met betrekking tot de vraag of de conclusies nawerkbaar zijn, worden gemaakt:

Zie aparte bladzijde

Re Item V

Reasoned statement with regard to novelty, inventive step or industrial applicability; citations and explanations supporting such statement

- 1 Reference is made to the following document:
D1 NL 1 040 124 C (SMART FREQUENCIES B V) 25 september 2014
(2014-09-25)
- 2 D1 is regarded as being the prior art closest to the subject-matter of claim 1, and discloses an impedance spectrometer for the analysis of chemical compounds and ions in water in which sensor spots on a PCB are exposed to the water-based sample and impedance changes detected and monitored.
The subject-matter of claim 1 therefore differs from this known sensor in the provision of essentially two discrete capacitive sensors in parallel and is therefore new.
The problem to be solved by the present invention may be regarded as that of improving the accuracy and robustness of water sensing technology
None of the cited or consulted documents however suggests the present solution, which is the use of two sensor units in a parallel arrangement. Additionally, the sensor device of claim 1 is simple to manufacture. As this solution is also not considered obvious per se, it is seen to involve an inventive step.
The same reasoning applies, mutatis mutandis, to the subject-matter of the corresponding independent claim 15, which therefore is also considered new and inventive.
- 3 Claims 2-14 are dependent on one or more independent claims whose subject-matter is considered as being new and inventive, as discussed above, and as such said dependent claims also meet the requirements of novelty and inventive step.

Re Item VIII

Certain observations on the application

- 4 It is not clear from the application as a whole, whether first affinity layer 3 and second affinity layer 7 are intended to be identical or different, even when taking the knowledge of the skilled man into account, thus leading to a potential lack of disclosure in the application as a whole.

- 4.1 Claims 5-11 do not meet the requirements of clarity in that the matter for which protection is sought is not clearly defined. The functional statements "voor de detectie van ..." in each claim do not enable the skilled person to determine which technical features are necessary to perform the stated functions. Although the skilled man might assume this relates to the use of a different polymer affinity layer, this is not entirely obvious from the claim, even when read in the light of the description.